

Introducing
**Itihase
Hatekhari**

.....
Interactions with Children

Kolkata, November 2022

The brochure is a part of the IDSK-RLS project 'Revisiting the Craft of History Writing for Children (2022)'

Write up

Anwasha Sengupta

Debarati Bagchi

Illustrations

Participants of
the Story-telling Sessions

Design and Concept

Wasim Helal

Institute of Development Studies Kolkata

DD 27/D, Sector I, Kolkata -700064

Website: www.idsk.edu.in

Email- idsk@idskmail.com / office@idsk.edu.in

Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung South Asia

Liaison Office: New Delhi

C 15, SDA Market, New Delhi - 110016

Website: <https://www.rosalux.in>

email : south-asia@rosalux.org

This online publication is sponsored by the Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung with grants from the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development of the Federal Republic of Germany. This publication or parts of it can be used by others for free as long as they provide a proper reference to the original publication.

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About the Project

As a part of the project 'Revisiting the Craft of History Writing for Children (2022)', three illustrated history books were produced namely Itihase Hatekhari: Deshbhag (by Anwesha Sengupta), Itihase Hatekhari: Desher Bhasha (by Debarati Bagchi), Itihase Hatekhari: Desher Manush (by Tista Das). The illustrations were done by Ranjit Chitrakar and Siraj Chitrakar – two community artists from rural Bengal (potua or scroll painters) in collaboration with Wasim Helal, the Art Director. Children's encounter with the past, both in the domain of formal education and in the society they grow up in, is often shaped by stories, notions and symbols of the society, community, and nation-states that they learn to see as sacrosanct. The various kinds of violence inherent to the making of nation, society and community are either invisibilised or distorted in this process. In India, therefore, children's understanding of the past is often shaped by patriarchal, majoritarian and statist values. The above-mentioned books intended to write in a way that would unsettle such ideas by creatively revisiting the histories of nation-building, national belonging, and various other identities like language. The larger purpose was to write lucid narratives of how the contested borders and belongings of South Asia were historically produced. The books were written in Bengali. While limited print copies were circulated free of cost among various school teachers, schools, libraries, NGOs, press and policy-makers, pdfs were made freely available on several websites and were circulated widely through emails and social media.

About the Brochure

In this brochure we have collated the responses of children regarding the three books. We conducted several story-telling workshops where they were encouraged to draw and/or write on the themes that our books cover – like border, migration, meanings of India/Indian and linguistic diversity. Apart from that, we have received some feedback from children over emails. At present we have more than 130 feedback – including both the illustrations and the written responses. In this brochure we have selected twenty-four illustrations and organized them thematically. Here we have documented children's perceptions of border, migration, idea of the nation and its citizens and linguistic plurality.

Students who attended the physical sessions did not have the opportunity to read the books before the workshops. They listened to our readings and discussions and then wrote/drew on the basis of their own understandings and imaginations. The responses we received via email were from the children who had already read the entire books (pdfs). The different nature of engagements with the texts is apparent in the responses. Moreover, the students who attended the physical workshops overwhelmingly belong to urban poor families (except the attendees of the Shantiniketan workshop, more on this in the following section) with no cultural capital. While looking at the responses, the heterogeneity of the children needs to be kept in mind.

Storytelling Sessions with Children

On **5 November 2022**, we had our first interaction with children. We spent the entire day with students of schools run by the Sanghati collective (known as Sanghati School or Solidarity School) and Anandagoshti (also known as Saturday School). Sanghati is an initiative of Bastibashi Sramajibi Adhikar Raksha Committee – a part of Mazdoor Adhikar Sangharsh Abhiyan (MASA). They run five schools for slum children in five different locations in Kolkata. Underprivileged children of these slums are mostly enrolled in public schools, but free classes at Sanghati schools assist them in the learning process. Most of the teachers at Sanghati also belong to these slums and they have day-jobs in the informal labour sector of the city (mason, plumber, driver etc.). They are active participants of MASA and have finished high school or college. They take classes in the evening according to a predetermined schedule. Two of the five schools operate under flyover and three operate at rented rooms in the slums. Anandagoshti school is conducted in the premises of the Institute of Development Studies Kolkata (IDSK). PhD students of the institute run this weekly school for children living in the adjacent slum. We met 45 children from these schools and read portions from the book on partition – Deshbhag. We also watched a film together on the story of two friends Mukund and Riyaz who were separated at the time of partition.

On **6 November 2022**, we conducted a story-telling session with 53 students of Rokeya Shikshakendra. We discussed the book on language and identities – Desher Bhasha. Most of the children were from migrant families who live in the low-income housing quarters of the Baishnabghata-Patuli locality in South Kolkata. They soon started having conversations amongst themselves about their different mother tongues – some of them knew Bhojpuri, some could speak in the dialects of East Bengal. After listening to the story of language movement and creation of Bangladesh, four students sang a song on the International Mother Language Day. On both the days, Ranjit and Sirajudaula Chitrakar, illustrators of the books, conducted painting sessions with the kids. Sirajudaula told the kids about scroll painters and their techniques. The kids drew pictures on how they understand borders, migration and language diversity in the country.

On **8 November 2022**, we met a small group of 11 children at Batighar Pathshala, an evening school in the Kalighat area of South Kolkata run by the Bondhu Collective. This community school also teaches and trains students who are enrolled at government schools. Many of them are children of sex workers who live in the locality. Some of them come from families of informal workers who have migrated to the city. We discussed the meanings of borders, linguistic diversity of our country and contestations around language with this group of bright and enthusiastic kids. All of them wrote a sentence on how they conceive the meaning of border. While some associated the meaning of border with something that our country 'protects', others saw it just as a line that separates. Some of the kids also wrote how borders are not good since they divide people.

On **21 November 2022**, we visited the Sishutirtha school in Shantiniketan. The school is run by a trust that also runs an orphanage. We had a session with children from classes four and five. Most of them came from middle and upper middle class families settled in Shantiniketan. On this day, we discussed the book *Deshar Manush* with the kids. We read stories from the book and engaged them in various activities. They wrote and drew pictures of who they think are the people of our country. We also played a fun game with them to make them understand how people are identified in terms of their language, region, religion and country and how these identities often overlap. They were asked to pick chits of papers that had different names of linguistic and religious identities.

How Children Perceive 'Borders'

Drawing from the responses, we could locate distinct tendencies of the perception of borders among the kids. In many of their illustrations, we can discern symbols and representations of hypernationalism. Many such representations of borders try to capture a child's idea of courage, bravery, patriotism.

How Children Perceive
'Borders'

Shamim

class VI,
story-telling
session 1

Shamim explains, his drawing shows India launching missiles in the direction of Pakistan and an Indian soldier is saluting the tricolour at the India-Pakistan border.

How Children Perceive 'Borders'

Aahan
Poddar

class V,
story-telling
session 3

Aahan explains 'my drawing has a number of soldiers from the Indian army on one side, they are showing respect to the flag. On the other side of the border Talibans are conspiring to make an attack'. Shamim insists that Indians will win the war.

How Children Perceive 'Borders'

Piu
Mondol

class V,
story-telling
session 2

In this illustration, we can see the flags of Bangladesh and India standing at two corners. Four people of two different religions stand adjacent to the flags. The people, although divided by a border in reality, emerge as very similar in Piu's inclusive picture. 'Border' is not an obvious element in the image, but is inherent in the message that it conveys.

Sayan Mandal

class V,
story-telling
session 1

This is a reproduction of the story of Joymoni from the book 'Deshbhag'. The story of Joymoni, the elephant, was read out during the workshop. Sayan heard the story and imagined and drew a picture by himself. This picture does not have much resemblance with the illustration of the book. The child introduces new elements like a barbed wire, two men wearing clothes that represent the flags of the two countries separated by the border. The illustration reveals that he could grasp the story entirely.

How Children Perceive 'Borders'

Payel
Dutta

class III,
story-telling
session 1

Payel has drawn a river border with Indian and Bangladeshi boats floating on it. The two sides of the river, although separated, appear to be very similar. In this session, the arbitrariness of the Bengal border and the problems of using the river as an international border was discussed. Payel's illustration reflects that she understood the discussion and could deploy her imagination.

Migration

in children's imaginations

Migration was another central theme of the first story-telling workshop.

In the film *Mukund and Riyaz* we see Mukund migrating from Karachi to India because of the partition riot.

We also read out the story of Deshraj from the book *Deshbhag* which focused on many migrations of Deshraj (first from Pakistan to India and then within India). Many of the children attending the session had direct experiences of rural-urban migration as their families had moved to Calcutta from villages of Bengal in search of work. They had extended families, friends and distant relatives back in the village and some of them routinely went back during festive season or according to the cultivation circle. Some of the children drew detailed images of their journeys from city to village or the reverse.

Migration

in children's imaginations

Mongol Paik

class VI,
story-telling
session 1

In this drawing we can see a train and a railway station named Joynagar. Two men are standing at the station with their bags. Mongol, who himself is from Joynagar, has named the illustration 'On the way from village to town'.

Migration

in children's imaginations

Imtara
Khatun

Class VI,
story-telling
session 1

Imtara has drawn a bus carrying passengers. When asked, she said that this was a bus from Salt Lake to Malda. Salt Lake (Kolkata) is where Imtara stays with her parents who work in the city and Malda is where her extended family lives.

Migration

in children's imaginations

Aloka Mandal

class VI,
story-telling
session 1

In her illustration we can see a mother and a child walking towards the river with their luggage. Aloka, in her conversation with us, informed us that the journey from Kolkata to her village involves multiple changes of transport including taking a boat to cross a river. She always travels with her mother and this illustration depicts a part of their journey towards their village.

Migration

in children's imaginations

Oishee
Dutta

class VIII

We received this illustration via email. Oishee had read the pdfs of all three books and then she had heard the experiences of her grandfather who had to migrate from East Pakistan to Calcutta because of partition. Her grandfather took a train during the riots and reached India amidst great danger. Oishee sent us this illustration with a detailed note on her grandfather's journey. In this illustration we can see a train coming from Bangladesh (East Pakistan till 1971) to India and she has named the illustration 'The Pain of Partition'. The image symbolizes the painful migration of the refugees during partition. Oishee's feedback was sought on the manuscripts of our books.

We, the People of India

We asked the children, 'who do you think are the people of India?'
We got varied responses from them. Their illustrations also reflected the diversity of the category 'Indian' and their notion of India. In the imagination of a few, India is a land of diverse religion and attire.

We, the People of India

Aniya
Halder

class VI,
story-telling
session 2

In this picture, three men could be seen, one in a so-called Sikh attire (turban and beard), another wears a fez cap representing a Muslim man and the third man does not have any obvious symbol of his religion.

We, the People of India

Santanu Ghosh

class VIII,
story-telling
session 2

This picture also has three men who could be identified with three separate religions by their attire – one in turban, another in fez cap and beard and the third in saffron dhoti and sikha (a particular hairstyle of practicing Hindu brahmins).

We, the People of India

Shubhankar
Mondal

class VIII,
story-telling
session 2

In this picture we see a boat in the river. The boat has two passengers - one with sikha (practicing Hindu Brahmin) and the other wearing a fez cap and sporting a beard (Muslim). They are smiling and standing side by side which shows amiability among them. Though there is no symbol directly depicting India, we have put this image in this section as this was drawn after we had an elaborate discussion about national belonging in India.

We, the People of India

Srotoswini

Class V,
story-telling
session 4

This illustration is strikingly different. In this image we see a young Hindu couple (wearing tilak, head gear like some North Indian Hindu men wear). Behind them there is a tree where one can find diyas (lamps) that are generally used during Hindu festivals like diwali or to worship Hindu gods, the symbol 'om' (another marker of Hindutva) and the Indian flag. After asking her we learnt that she thought both the tricolour and 'om' symbolizes India. She had heard that somewhere which she could not recall. Problematic though it is, such conflation reveals how right wing political groups have appropriated the idea of India. Others imagined India as a land of ordinary people: villagers, peasants, labourers and soldiers.

We, the People of India

Oyindralla Saha

Class V,
story-telling
session 4

In this illustration we see two dhoti clad men and a cow. She told us that she had drawn people from Ballavpur - a village near Shantiniketan, where she lives. Further, she added, these men were farmers.

We, the People of India

Atif

class V,
story-telling
session 4

In this striking image we see a man carrying loads on his head. It is difficult to say what the man is carrying, but it seems like coal. When asked, Atif did not specify. By using the tricolour as the background, Atif locates the labourer in India.

We, the People of India

Shinjan
Mukherjee

class V,
story-telling
session 4

In this illustration we see three men working in the field. Shinjan has named his illustration 'People of India'. When asked what is Indian about them, he told us that he had seen similar fields and peasants in the villages near Shantiniketan, which is in India.

We, the People of India

Rupkatha

class IX

In this illustration we see a series of camps and a large crowd of people around them. They are partition refugees waiting for their accommodation at the camps, Rupkatha told us. Apart from our books, Rupkatha has learned about partition from her family which had migrated from East Pakistan after 1947 and from various books. Rupkatha's feedback was sought on the manuscripts of our books.

We, the People of India

Dijottama

class V,
story-telling
session 4

Dijottama has recently shifted from the USA to India and now lives in Shantiniketan. However, her sense of belonging differed from other kids of her class. While drawing the people of the country, she drew a scene from her neighbourhood in America and her best friend who still lives there. Although she is an Indian, she still has a strong attachment to the country where she has lived for so many years.

Children's encounter with **Languages**

We interacted with the children on the diversity of languages in our country. The kids were quite excited to relate this with their own classroom experience. Coming from migrant families, many of them had different mother tongues apart from Bengali. Also, they all did not speak the same Bengali, some were fluent in the Kolkata dialect, others in the eastern Bengali dialect. We asked them to think of places where people speaking many languages gather at one place. They came up with very interesting ideas and drew pictures of markets, schools, galleries of stadiums and added speech bubbles to them. Some of them were not very clear about the overlaps of religion and language and often separated them.

**Simran
Halder**

class IX,
story-telling
session 2

This picture speaks of how people of different languages live in the same locality or neighbourhood in our country and they greet each other in their own ways when they meet. The woman is asking a man in an eastern Bengali dialect if he is doing well. There are two other men, who are exchanging greetings that are associated with Sikhs and Muslims living in different regions.

Children's encounter with
Languages

**Suchismita
Baidya**

class VIII,
story-telling
session 2

Suchismita looks at school as a place where children coming from different language backgrounds meet, and also a place where they learn many languages. In this picture we can see three friends entering their school. They wish 'happy birthday' in English, but get 'dhanyabad' as a reply in Bengali.

Suraiya
Sarder

class IX,
story-telling
session 2

This picture connects language and religion. The caption says - 'people from different religions wish to live together'. A Hindu man, with a temple in his background, greets with a namaskar and calls the Muslim man 'bhaijaan'. The muslim man, with a mosque in the background greets with what is commonly known as Muslim greeting - 'as-salamu alaykum'.

**Titli
Mukherjee**

class IX,
story-telling
session 2

The idea that inspired this picture was how markets can be meeting places for people speaking different languages. People can be seen asking the price of things, some others are chatting. The speech bubbles show they are speaking in various languages.

Titli Mistri

class VII,
story-telling
session 2

Titli lives at the Rokeya school with her favourite Mamata didi who takes care of cooking and other chores. She plans to open a vegetable shop someday with Mamata. So, she has drawn a picture of 'Mamata-Titli Enterprise'. A woman is asking for the price of a potato in Bengali and gets a reply in Hindi.

**Narayan
Mondal**

class IX,
story-telling
session 2

The children at Rokeya school had read about the international mother language day in their school. They were very excited to listen to the story of the language movement in Bangladesh. Some even sang a song in the memory of the movement. In this picture, Narayan has drawn the picture of a leader asking the Bengalis to wake up and fight for their mother tongue.

Our Observations

Content and Readability

a

The first three sessions were held at various community schools attended by the students from different marginal communities of Kolkata. The last session, held at Shantiniketan Shishutirtha, was attended by students belonging to more well-off families. The difference in cultural capital, access to the internet and other infrastructure is apparent from the writing abilities of the children. The long lockdown due to covid 19 pandemic has accentuated the implications of class differences among the school going children. From the registration sheet of the first story-telling session attended by the children of Sanghati and Anandagoshthi (November 5 2022), we can see how the attendees struggled to write their names, the names of their schools and classes. Similarly, at Batighar Pathshala (8 November 2022), most of the attendees could not construct correct sentences or could write correct spelling. The vocabulary, ability to read and write of the Shishutirtha students, on the other hand, was way better. Their resources and cultural capital had helped them in continuing with their education during the covid lockdown. For many students who attended our sessions on November 5 and November 8, our books are difficult reads. But the teachers of Sanghati School, who themselves belong to the underprivileged section of the society, showed great interest in our books. Biswajit Haldar, the person in charge of Sanghati School, told us that such books are important as teachers often

struggle for good content that can be used at the schools. Three teachers have already read all the books and have read out portions of it in their classes. Similar sentiments were echoed by Smritiparna, who is in charge of Batighar Pathshala. The principal of Shantiniketan Shishutirtha, Mr. Sudripta Tagore, on the other hand informed us that these books can be used for even younger kids, like classes IV and V (age 10-11) in his school.

b

At Rokeya Shikshakendra, however, the overall standard of writing capacity and vocabulary is better than Batighar and Sanghati/Saturday School. In our understanding, this can be explained through better infrastructure. At Rokeya there are more than 50 teachers for around 100 students; the house from where Rokeya School operates has six rooms and classes are held daily in two shifts. Students of different standards are grouped separately and taught separately. At the other community schools, there is one room or a garage where all the students - irrespective of their classes - are taught together. Therefore, at Rokeya, the students get more focused i

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individual attention, that too daily. Consequently, their capacity to read, write and articulate is far better than the pupils of other community schools. As the teachers of Rokeya told us and our observations also tally, the students of Rokeya who are within the age bracket of 12 and 14 years will be able to read Ithase Hatekhari books without parental/teachers' help. At Rokeya, they have a functional library with stipulated library hours where every student is encouraged to read outside the syllabus. We have been informed that already around 10 students have read portions of the three books, or the entire books.

From the above two points, we conclude that the reading/writing ability of middle school students vary widely. Such variations are caused by structural inequalities. Hence, students who are below 12 years or above 14 years may find our books interesting, depending on their reading/writing capability.

Our Observations

Illustrations

a

The illustrations by the students from all the story-telling sessions reveal that they closely listened to our readings and discussions and could both comprehend and easily relate to our books. They used their own experiences and the instances taken from their familiar world to make sense of the books.

b

The use of pwochitra (scroll painting) and the drawing sessions were greatly appreciated by the children. The techniques followed by the community artists to extract colour from various natural ingredients seemed particularly fascinating to the children. Rokeya Shikshakendra has already approached Siraj Chitrakar for conducting a two day workshop on pwochitra with their students during the summer vacation in 2023.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We gratefully acknowledge the institutional support received from the Institute of Development Studies Kolkata and the financial support received from Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung South Asia. We would also like to thank the following individuals/institutions for helping us organizing the story telling sessions: Biswajit, Anirban, Biswajit Chakrabarty, Mamoni, Jahar and other teachers of Sanghati School (Solidarity School), Pallavi, Sharanya, Ronojoy, Usha, Parimal and others of Anandagoshti (Saturday School), Kasturi and others of Rokeya Shikshakendra, Piya and Smritiparna of Batighar Pathshala, Sudripta Tagore and all the teachers of Shantiniketan Sishutirtha School. We are also grateful to Ranjit Chitrakar and Sirajudulla Chitrakar for facilitating the drawing sessions.

OUR TEAM

Writers

Anwasha Sengupta, Tista Das, Debarati Bagchi

Illustrators

Ranjit Chitrakar, Sirajudulla Chitrakar

Art director

Wasim Helal

To access the books write to us at
childrenhistorybooks@gmail.com
or scan the QR codes

ITIHAASE HATEKHARI: DESHVAG
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7119367>

ITIHAASE HATEKHARI : DESHER BHASHA
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7270812>

ITIHAASE HATEKHARI: DESHER MANUSH
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118653>

